

THE HUMAN-CENTERED APPROACH IN LINGUISTICS: EMBRACING THE ANTROPOCENTRIC PARADIGM

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Abstract:

The antropocentric paradigm in linguistics places human beings at the core of linguistic analysis, emphasizing the role of language in human communication, cognition, and social interactions. This article explores the principles and implications of this paradigm, which recognizes language as a social phenomenon shaped by cultural contexts. It highlights the cognitive and psychological dimensions of language, values linguistic diversity, and encourages interdisciplinary approaches. Embracing the antropocentric paradigm offers a holistic understanding of language as a dynamic and multifaceted human phenomenon.

Keywords: antropocentric paradigm, linguistics, human-centered approach, language and cognition, social interactions, cultural contexts, linguistic diversity, interdisciplinary, cognitive dimensions, holistic understanding

The field of linguistics has undergone significant shifts in theoretical perspectives and paradigms over the years. One such paradigm that has gained prominence is the human-centered or antropocentric approach. This approach places human beings at the center of linguistic analysis, emphasizing the role of language in human communication, cognition, and social interactions. In this article, we explore the key principles and implications of the antropocentric paradigm in linguistics.

The connection between language and thought is revealed in this field, and now the focus is not on the structural study of the language, but on the way information is received, perceived, and new ones appear in the mind of the user, language or speaker¹

The antropocentric paradigm in linguistics recognizes the fundamental connection between language and human beings. It acknowledges that language

¹ Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2023). The Issues Related to Studying of Language and thought in Cognitive Linguistics. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 271-273.

is a uniquely human phenomenon, deeply intertwined with our cognitive abilities, cultural practices, and social dynamics. Unlike earlier approaches that focused primarily on formal structures and abstract systems, the antropocentric paradigm places emphasis on the lived experiences of language users and the social and cultural contexts in which language is used.

The antropocentric paradigm views language as a social phenomenon that is shaped by and shapes human interactions. It recognizes that language is not simply a set of formal rules or structures, but a dynamic tool used by individuals to engage with others and construct meaning. Language is seen as a means of communication, identity formation, and social cohesion. This perspective highlights the importance of studying language in real-life contexts and considering the social and cultural factors that influence its use.

Another key aspect of the antropocentric paradigm is its focus on the cognitive and psychological dimensions of language. It recognizes that language is not only a tool for communication but also a cognitive system that plays a crucial role in human cognition and thought processes. Language structures and influences our perception, problem-solving abilities, and conceptualizations of the world. By studying language from a cognitive perspective, linguists gain insights into how language shapes our thinking and understanding of the world.

What language is, how it appears, and what kind of phenomenon it is, have been the cause of debate by scientists since the emergence of linguistics. Looking back at history, many studies have been conducted to determine whether language is a natural or a social phenomenon. This is important not only in traditional linguistics but also in modern linguistics. Noam Chomsky, who is considered the father of modern linguistics, although this idea is not approved by most linguists, in his theory of universal grammar, all languages have similar structures and rules, children everywhere learn the language without the same difficulty that he was born with existing basic knowledge and the ability to understand language.²

The antropocentric paradigm also embraces the rich variation and diversity of language. It acknowledges that languages and dialects vary across communities, regions, and cultures. This perspective values linguistic diversity and recognizes the importance of studying and preserving different languages and language varieties. By studying language variation, linguists gain a deeper understanding of the complex relationship between language, culture, and identity.

²E.Saphir.Language: An Introduction to the Study of Speech.1921

The antropocentric paradigm has several practical implications for linguistic analysis. It encourages researchers to adopt interdisciplinary approaches, drawing from fields such as anthropology, sociology, psychology, and cognitive science. It also emphasizes the importance of conducting empirical research and using qualitative and quantitative methods to study language in its natural contexts. This paradigm encourages linguists to engage with language users, communities, and cultures, fostering collaboration and co-creation of knowledge.

The antropocentric paradigm also highlights the ethical considerations involved in linguistic research. It underscores the need for researchers to respect the linguistic rights and cultural practices of the communities they study. Linguistic analysis should be carried out with sensitivity and an awareness of the potential impact on individuals and communities.

The antropocentric paradigm in linguistics brings a fresh perspective to the study of language, placing human beings at the center of linguistic analysis. By recognizing the social, cognitive, and cultural dimensions of language, this paradigm offers a holistic understanding of language as a complex and dynamic human phenomenon. Embracing the antropocentric paradigm allows linguists to explore the intricate interplay between language and human experiences, leading to valuable insights into communication, cognition, and social interactions.

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